

PAINTING EPOCH AND SENSE: A FORMAL INSPECTION

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Abstract

The tradition of painting that has been around for a long time is called the epoch of painting. And the change in modern times is called the meaning of sense in painting. As the Aadimanav became civilized, the Indian conditions changed. Religion and spirituality were given important place in Indian culture. In India, internal beauty has always been given precedence over external beauty. Therefore, in India's painting, the emotional side became clearer and more emerging.

Due to political upheaval in India and some political reasons, the influence of Greek art is seen on the painting of India. Then came the golden age of Indian culture, which is considered Ajanta. The works of this era are considered to be the best.

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1. Introduction

The history of Indian painting dates back to the era of Ajanta, Ellora and other murals. Other famous examples are Buddhist palm leaf manuscripts, the Jain texts and the Deccan, Mughal and Kangda schools. Indian paintings are a portrayal of tradition and depiction of ancient texts and theories in color and anecdotal accounts. It was common during the ancient times have paintings in households in the doorways or indoor rooms where guests resided.

After considering ancient Indian art, it is known that sculpture and architecture got special encouragement in Pal era. Artists sculpted at this time, inspired by Buddhism and Hinduism. At this time, more idols of deities and huge temples were built. The Pala dynasty slowly began to decline after the twelfth century. After this, Bihar was divided into many smaller states. Many idols were also built during the Mauryan period and the Gupta period. The idol craft of this time was at its peak. With the gradual arrival of Turks-Afghans in India, the Mughal era rites began to be incorporated into Indian traditional art. After that the British came to India commercially. He started the business of Indian paintings, as a result of which the Indian art market flourished for years.

2. Epoch of Painting

There has been a sense of indifference to painting in the religion of Islam. Therefore, the development of Indian painting came to a standstill in the early period of Muslim rule. But during Akbar, there was a change in this ideology. The Persian style began to influence the Indian style and a new style of Mughal style was born. Many religious texts were decorated during the Mughal period and painting started to flourish again. After the end of Mughal rule this painting remained confined to the native states. Meanwhile, Rajasthani, Kangda and Pahari style paintings were made. After this, the British came to India with an orthodox culture in which external beauty was given more importance. This style also influenced Indian painters.

The Mughal zamindars from Delhi, art lovers were respected as their court artists. It was a matter of prestige for him to have artists in his court. Another cast team settled in the foothills of the Himalayas and other remaining artists settled in Lucknow, Banaras, Murshidabad, Hyderabad and Mysore. The artists settled in the hill areas gave rise to the hill style. At the present time, the painting has been divided into two parts, Fine Art and Commercial Art. In fine art, expression is given importance in expressions and commercialism.

The history of Indian art is developing. The history of Indian art is associated with the decline of traditional Rajasthani, Pahadi and Mughal art styles and the establishment of English rule in India. As the influence of the East-India Company established by the British in India increased, so did the rule of many states, by removing all the rulers from India or entering into a treaty with them and took control of the East India Company. The rulers of Indian states, under the British rule, painters who were under the royal rule also escaped from their shelter.

The East India Company brought some of its leading painters to India. Indian artists, disdaining their traditional art styles, started following painters and their art from the West, and a new art style came to be known as the company style. Now in the traditional style of India, along with Mughal elements, the European elements also started getting incorporated. Due to which the Indian style did not survive in its original state and Indian traditional styles were greatly shocked. But

some local styles were still defending themselves, including Pat Chitra of Kalighat, Pat Chitra of Nathdwara, Tanjore style Pat Chitra, Orissa Pat Chitra etc.

3. Sense of Painting

The artist must know about his history and tradition, because the artist develops his own and his own art from his history and tradition. He tries to understand whether the traditional element is capable of giving expression to his experiences or not? Will he be able to keep unexpected emotions fresh from him? If not, he has to find new mediums that suit his creation and work. This is the reason that active artists always resort to new mediums to create new designs. Motion and change always communicate strength in art.

For example, stagnant water starts to deteriorate after some time, due to being stable in one place, it becomes inert, it does not remain clean and clean like running water. The same situation is also with art. The vastness, diversity and continuity of art are considered. The change in tradition and culture is an hour of development of art. This shows that we do not forget our culture and tradition, just change it according to time.

Today's modern artist resorts to historical and mythological themes for new sensations. But this will be possible only when the artist has complete knowledge of the subject. Modern art has been greatly influenced by art professionals and critics. Central and state academies and voluntary organizations also have a big place to influence art. These institutions were created to disseminate art, but these institutions create a low-level political month among artists. And nowadays these institutions have started organizing awards which have also created a low-level political month among the artists. But the identity of the artist is deeply reflected in his creativity, stability and art.

Modern Indian art has undergone more changes in contemporary times than in ancient times. Before understanding the changes in contemporary Indian art, we have to understand the changes in the art of the whole world. There is freedom in the whole world, which has come from political consciousness. In the era of computerization and modernization, a person has been able to make his own special identity, and has emerged as a dominant figure in the society. Along with the development of his own and society, he also developed means of transport and means of communication, which made his life easier and came closer to each other. With the development of modern equipment such as radios, newspapers, TV, books, computers etc., the scope of work capacity of human beings was increased. Now news of the stir of the world stage is immediately received. These inventions also brought a lot of change in art and the scope of art also increased. Today's artists are surrounded by instruments, due to which the entire world revolves around instruments. Now the artist has started getting detailed information about art easily and more conveniently. This increased the scope of art. By the nineteenth century, newspapers, cameras, etc. had been invented, so Avindranath Tagor, Nandlal Bose, etc. we're not only influenced by Indian traditions, but they were from the countries of West, China and Japan etc. I also learned a lot. Many artists of the nineteenth century were influenced by countries such as the West, China and Japan.

4. Conclusion

Looking at the history of art, we get to know that the artist was bound in bondage, he was not free to express his feelings. Paintings developed in places like Jainism, Jainism, Hinduism and Ajanta, Ellora, Rajasthan, etc., were composed on the immediate topics of social as well as religion. Now artists were beginning to feel free to express their feelings. After getting rid of all the shackles, artists began to consider art as a means of sensuality. With which he started doing new experiments in his art and mediums. This developed instinct led artists to feel free to express themselves. Now artists started working for "Swat Sukhay", not for the fulfillment of wishes.

The arrival of the British brought a lot of change in Indian art. The Englishmen brought cameras with them, which led to an interest in the artist in the three-dimensional space. British state administration proved to be a major hindrance in the development of Indian art. Modern art was born in the environment of social consciousness movement and Indian independence movement.

Indian artists did not pay much attention to stereotyping. Or we can say that he had a low tendency towards three-dimensional marking. Yamini Rai, Amrita Shergil, Bendre, Panikkar, Ara, Hussain, Hebbar etc., expressed their desire to create a new dimension in the world of art by drawing two-dimensional drawings and expressing Indian life by simplified designs. Have resorted to tantric counterparts etc. These artists also expressed their desire to express new dimensions in the picture world by expressing simplified forms of Indian life through two-dimensional painting, with literary patterns. The paintings of Indian artists were influenced by Impressionism, Cubist etc. The influence of Eastern and Western working methods can be seen in the Indian painting tradition.

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